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Influence of [Bmim]⁺ ion concentration and linear flow velocity on the limiting current density during electro dialysis process

Ionic liquids (ILs) are a group of compounds gaining an important role in the fields of chemistry and environmental protection. Unfortunately, due to the good miscibility of ILs with most solvents, their recovery and separation from the solution by classical separation methods is often inefficient. One of the method used for IL recovery can be electro dialysis (ED). The important parameter in the description of ED is the limiting current density (LCD). Thus, the aim of this work is to determine the influence of [Bmim]⁺ ion concentration and linear flow velocity on the LCD during ED.

The ED experiments were carried out using an EDR-Z/10-0.8 module (MemBrain, Czech Republic) with an effective single-membrane area of 64 cm². There were five pairs of membranes in the ED stack. The ion-exchange membranes (IEMs) used in this investigations were heterogeneous AM(H)-CM(H) (Ralex, Czech Republic). The LCDs were determined based on current–voltage curves using the Cowan–Brown method, for solutions with [Bmim]Cl concentrations of 0.01, 0.05, 0.10, 0.25, and 0.50 mol/L, at various linear flow velocity (1-5 cm/s). The applied voltage was increased stepwise at a rate of 0.5 V/min. The concentrations of the [Bmim]Cl solutions were determined with a UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Varian Cary 50 Scan, Agilent, USA).

In this work the LCDs in the assumed ED parameters were determined. As suspected, the LCD depended upon the [Bmim]Cl concentration in the diluate solution and linear flow velocity. It was proven that the LCD increased linearly with increasing [Bmim]Cl concentration in the diluate and linear flow velocity.

Keywords: ionic liquids recovery, 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride, limiting current density, electro dialysis

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